

CITIZEN SCIENCE FOR URBAN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: MAPPING SESSIONS TO IMPROVE WASTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

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Abstract: One of the main perspectives in the Europe 2020 Strategy is to progress towards the achievement of a Circular Economy. In this context, citizen science may play a key role to empower and involve citizenship in the co-creation of solutions to urban challenges. To this end, “Mapping Sessions” have been carried out within Waste4Think project. On one hand, geographic information has been collected by citizens to be used in the diagnosis and analysis of the waste management system. It will ease the definition and implementation of innovative measures regarding urban planning and policy making. On the other hand, citizens, with no specific professional skills, are actively involved in scientific tasks facilitating the generation of this new knowledge. Finally, citizens acquire new knowledge regarding municipal needs as well as skills in technology.

Keywords: Citizen science, urban planning, sustainability, governance, citizen empowerment.

2. Introduction

Citizen science can play a key role in urban development involving the participation of volunteers in the scientific process. Its use in domains of science such as urban design [1, 2], health [3] or environmental protection [4, 5] is well demonstrated. In this work how citizen science and volunteered geographic information can contribute to improve the municipal waste management services is presented. To this end different mapping sessions using mobile phones and tablets have been carried out. The aim of this citizen science activity is multiple: 1) To gather spatial information about the urban facilities and the level of accessibility, 2) To provide skills in Information & Communication Technologies (ICT) and Geographical Information Systems (GIS) to citizens, 3) Recognition and validation of data by citizens, 4) To foster transparency and mechanisms for citizens to communicate their needs to the municipality, and 3) To provide information to policy makers and urban planners to ease the decision-making process.

3. Methodology

The Mapping Sessions have been developed in the Municipality of Zamudio (Spain). Its main objective was the creation of an inventory of the municipal facilities, economical activities and other elements, such as accessibility level, at municipal scale. For the field work, 9 different groups were created and the members were trained in terms of the information to be retrieved and the tools to be used for its collection: GPS (Global Positioning Systems) and forms using mobile devices and 8 analogic maps. Information regarding economical activities (type, name, address...), deposit points (containers, bins, clean or recycling points, sorting type, volume, level of accessibility, identification tags, status...) and accessibility level (street map, height and width of sidewalks, presence of steps at the entrance to the portals, availability of lift in buildings...) was collected. Subsequently, a digitalization process and a topological validation of the information have been carried out. The generated shapefiles have been incorporated in the Open Source Platform OpenStreetMap (OSM) to share them and edit the digital information generated by other users. Also, 3D scene models have been created to ease their visualization to detect potential improvements for a more sustainable urban development.

4. Results

More than 9 km per group have been walked with a total of 3.840 sample points collected and involving 19 shapes (14 point type, 4 polygon type and 1 line type). With this information a municipal inventory of the deposit points has been built using 3D maps. Moreover the information collected is the basis to calculate the geographical WESTE (Economical-Technical-Social-Environmental) indicators [6] to evaluate the efficiency of the current system, such as the waste generation estimation per deposit point, the proximity and accessibility levels to the facilities or the quantification of the distances covered by the trucks to calculate the environmental impact of the routes. In this analysis it has been seen that only the 49% of the population is at a distance lower than 50 m to a deposit point. Figure 1 shows the results of the accessibility level of the population to the deposit points in terms of road safety. For this analysis it has been used the information regarding the localization of the deposit points as well as geographical aspects of the municipality (traffic lights, zebra crossings, sidewalks...) collected during the mapping sessions and digitalized in OSM. As result the municipal technicians have reallocated the containers to improve the accessibility and the capacity of the containers and consequently the efficiency of the service. The information is also shown in a public dashboard with the aim to foster the transparency of the system as well as the knowledge transfer to the rest of the citizens of the municipality.

Fig.1: Accessibility analysis of the population to the deposit points in Zamudio

5. Conclusions

Citizen science activities allow citizenship to participate of the scientific development and, by doing so, critical spirit is fostered, obtaining a well trained and environmentally aware community. On the other hand, policy makers and urban planners can take informed and more appropriate decisions to move towards more sustainable and inclusive cities.

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